

**STAKEHOLDERS PERCEPTION TOWARDS ABOLITION OF
RANKING OF STUDENTS AND SCHOOLS IN NATIONAL
EXAMINATIONS IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN KENYA:
A CASE OF WEST POKOT COUNTY**

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Abstract:

The government of Kenya abolished ranking among schools in the year 2014, which took effect from the year 2015. This was put in place in order to eliminate cut-throat competition among institutions and to end unethical practices by teachers in the rush for top positions. Abolition of ranking in West Pokot drew different reactions and perspectives from different stakeholders of education. The study examined stakeholders' perception towards abolition of ranking on students and schools in national examination in Secondary schools in Kenya. The objectives of the study were; to determine stakeholders' perception on ranking of schools, to determine how ranking of school affected students' commitment to academic performance, the impact of secondary school ranking on the parental commitment on students' academic matters and how ranking of schools influenced ministry of education officials and county officials' commitment to academic activities. The research design adopted in this study was cross sectional descriptive survey. Cluster sampling (probability sampling) and non-probability (purposive sampling) techniques were adopted to determine sample size. Questionnaire and interview guides were employed in data collection. Descriptive statistics and inferential statistics (chi-square) were adopted for quantitative data analysis. Qualitative data were categorized and analysed according to themes. Theoretical framework was based and guided by Talcott Persons Structural

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Functionalism Theory. In the conceptual framework, the independent variable in this research is the stakeholders' perception, while the dependent is the result of abolition. Findings from the study indicated that abolition of ranking had a lot of negative outcomes compared to positive effects and the decision be reverted for better results in our schools. The study concluded that, ranking motivates teachers to cover syllabus, change institutional practices, makes them focus their teaching activities towards examination neglecting other aspects of education but has no impact on their self-esteem. It also encourages completion among departments but can lead to unhealthy competition among different categories of schools. However, ranking leads to narrowing of curriculum and encourage malpractices in national examination. On students' commitment on academic performance, ranking acts as motivating factor to performing students but might destroy morale to underperforming ones. Students however become less concerned with performance when ranking is abolished. Abolition of ranking influences parents to buy extra teaching and learning materials. It also impacts negatively on parental involvement on school academic programs but does not influence parental support for homework. Abolition of ranking impacts negatively on ministry of education officials' commitment of academic matters at it affects their involvement in issues like resource allocations. The study recommends that; the decision of abolishing of ranking by government should be reverted or should be practiced by schools at different levels, it should also be done continuously throughout the academic year to get trends of performance and schools should provide psychological support to all students' especially underperforming ones. Education stakeholders should define measures to curb malpractices in examination among students and students and not to just abolish ranking.

Keywords: ranking, examinations, performance, perception, abolition

1. Introduction

In the United States, teachers' unions, school leaders, principals and teachers have tended to oppose policies linking assessment to accountability on the grounds of perverse effects including narrowing the curriculum to the practice of teaching to the test and incentives for teachers to cheat (Evers & Walberg, 2003). Evidence suggests that agencies alter the timing of their actions and engage in cream skimming in response to specific performance measures (Hickman, Henrick & Smith, 2002). They exclude weak students from sitting for examinations. Cheating was mentioned as another unproductive type of response to accountability incentives and misreporting of school

dropout rates (Peabody & Markley, 2003). Schools also excluded weak students by engaging in cream skimming at the point of admission. This is because the higher the ability of students admitted, the better the output and the higher the schools relative position in the league tables (Wilson, 2001). Performance tables for England have been published annually since 1992 (Wilson, 2003). Currently they are used to describe the difference between 'materials brought in and the finished product' and thus measures the value added by the production process (Wilson, 2003). However, other studies indicate that, despite the use of league tables in Kenya, Senegal and elsewhere, several factors indicate that their use is complicated and misleading. If students differ from school to school in their level of achievement when joining the schools, a measure of achievement at a later date that does not take this into account will be inequitable and misleading in that it will not adequately reflect a school's success in moving students from their initial entry level to their present level of achievement as reflected in a public examination (Kellaghan & Greaney, 2001).

In Kenya, ranking dates to as far back as colonial time. Kenyan education history started after the establishment of Local Native Council (LNC) and Independent Schools (Bogonko, 1992). These schools were ranked alongside the existing missionary schools and by the early 1940s; their performance was way above that of missionary schools. Ranking was also done among the Government African Schools (GAS) whose first batch of pupils sat the Primary School Examinations (PSE) in 1938. During colonial period, examinations were organized by the British. After independence, the organization of examinations was localized in East Africa. The Cambridge syndicate that was conducting examinations was replaced by East African Examinations Council in 1973 which offered East African Certificate of Education (EACE) and East African Advanced Certificate of Education (EAACE). In 1980, an act of parliament empowered the Kenya National Examination Council (KNEC) to manage examination in Kenyan schools (Eshiwani, 1993). With the introduction of 8-4-4 system of education, Certificate of Primary Education (CPE) was replaced by KCPE from 1984.

The Kenya Junior Secondary Examination (KJSE), Kenya Certificate of Education (KCE) Examination and Kenya Advanced Certificate of Education (KACE) Examination were also phased out in 1985, 1987 and 1989 in that order (Eshiwani, 1993). Under the 8-4-4 system, the four year secondary school education cycle ends with the Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education (KCSE) examination which replaced KCE in the old 7-4-2-3 system of education. This was followed by a radical change in the ranking of schools according to a performance index. Up to 2007, there have been seven categories of ranking examination results at the secondary school level used. These are: the overall, National schools, Provincial schools, District schools, Private schools, most

improved schools and Students' categories. The publication of mean performance statistics for the top schools in the respective categories and top students in the nation and provinces was meant to make it possible for schools to compare their performance with other schools. This form of ranking was strictly based on students' academic performance in national. It also fails to take into consideration the difference in facilities and students' intake mark in form one among other factors. West Pokot County is in the North Western part of Kenya in the North Rift region of the vast Rift Valley. Three quarter of the county is semi-arid making the residents of the area solely depend on livestock rearing.

There is low transition rate from Primary to Secondary in the county standing at 52%, while the national transition rate is 79% as at the year 2013. (District statistics office Kapenguria) The county of West Pokot has been doing well in national examinations for example in the year 2013 it was ranked second and fourth in the year 2014 in K.C.S.E. It is therefore against this backdrop that the study seeks to find out stakeholders perception towards school ranking on stakeholder commitment to academic performance in secondary schools.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

The ranking of Secondary schools and students in national examinations encourages positive competition. However, the extent to which this affects the commitment of the stakeholders in particular has been evidenced by mixed feelings and anxiety during the release of Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education (KCSE) results in February every year, when the names of students and schools have graced the print and electronic media. The posting of results has reinforced a widely held belief that there are good and bad schools in Kenya thus a possible effect on the general commitment of the stakeholders in academic performance. Despite the national ban on ranking, schools are still ranked at the County level, West Pokot being one of them. The mixed reactions range from praise and criticism for promoting unfair competition among schools because the comparison between schools fails to take into account differences in the KCPE intake mark, social and physical conditions under which the different schools operate. Ranking individual students and schools creates fierce competition which sometimes leads to departure from teaching to preparation for passing examinations and cheating. Therefore, it is against this background that this study intends to investigate the effects of the abolishment of secondary school rankings on the stakeholders' commitment to academic performance.

1.2 Purpose of the Study

The study examined stakeholders' perception towards abolition of ranking of students and schools in national examinations in secondary schools in Kenya.

1.3 Specific Objectives

1. To investigate stakeholders perception on abolition of ranking of schools in National examinations.
2. To establish the effect of abolition of school ranking on students' commitment to academic performance.
3. To determine how abolition of school ranking influences parents commitment to academic performance.
4. To examine how abolition of ranking influences Ministry of Education, Science and Technology and Education County officials commitment to academic performance in West Pokot County.

1.4 Null Hypothesis

The study was guided by the following null hypothesis:-

Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between syllabus coverage and Interschool competition.

Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between teaching / instructional practices and examination preparation.

Ho₃: There is no significant relationship between abolition of ranking and parental involvement in students' academic activities.

Ho₄: There is no significant relationship between students' level of performance and abolition of ranking.

1.5 Theoretical Framework

The study was guided by the Talcott Persons Structural Functionalism Theory. According to this theory, formal organizations consist of many groupings of different individuals, all working together harmoniously towards a common goal. The working could also be promoted by having the same commitment towards the achievement of a particular common goal. It argues that most organizations are large and complex social units consisting of many interacting sub-units which are sometimes in harmony but more often than not they are in diametric opposition to each other. Functionalism is concerned with the concept of order, formal work in organizations and in particular, how order seems to prevail in both systems and society irrespective of the changes in goals and commitment which constantly takes place. The theory seeks to understand

the relationship between the parts and the whole system in an organization and in particular identify how stability is for the most part achieved. In this case the commitment of stakeholders on academic performance could be facing a number of effects owing to a divided allegiance to either adopting raking fully of banning it. For the stakeholders to being committed fully towards academic performance, all the involved parties' have to function well and agree on a common course towards school ranking. The school as a social system has within its precincts a series of sub-systems which interact with each other and the environment. Their interactions should be harmonious for effective achievement of a common commitment towards academic performance.

1.6 Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework of the research has independent variable which is stakeholders' perception of the ranking of students and schools while the dependent is the result of abolition. It therefore links the research with its objectives hence making it binding. The consequent results that emanate from abolition of ranking can be felt in the case where students commitment decline.

Ranking of schools would encourage teachers' commitment to performance but since ranking is abolished, teachers become reluctant. The consequent result is decline in performance from all possible angles including stakeholders, and the various ministry officials. The hypothesized relationships between independent and dependent variables are illustrated in Figure 1;

2. Methodology

2.1 Research Design

The study was both quantitative and qualitative in nature. The research design adopted was a cross sectional descriptive survey. Descriptive survey is primarily concerned with determining “what is” (Mutai 2000). Its execution can yield important information about a phenomenon of study. Surveys are excellent vehicles for collecting original data for studying the attitudes and orientations of very large population. Using descriptive survey design, a large population can be studied with only a portion of that population being used to get required data. It is the most appropriate when the purpose of the study is to create a detailed description of phenomenon of study, (Wiersma & Jurs, 2005). Cluster sampling method was most preferred for this study because of its reliance on the views of the learners, teachers, and ministry officials among other stakeholders. Descriptive survey research design was ideal because it involves collecting quantitative and qualitative data in order to answer questions or test hypotheses concerning the current status of the subjects of the study (Kerlinger, 2000). According to Orodho (2009), the technique produces data that is holistic and in-depth. The design therefore will aid the researcher in examining the attitudes, opinions, perception and characteristics of the stakeholders’ commitment to ranking of schools in west Pokot County.

2.2 Target Population

The target population of the study comprised of students, teachers, principals, Ministry of education officers and county education officials. It consisted of two national schools, two extra county schools, County schools and four sub – County schools. According to Kerlinger, (2000), target population is the entire group of individuals, objects, item, cases, articles or things with common attributes or characteristics from which samples are taken for measurements is therefore a critical segment of the study since they possess crucial information about the problem under study.

2.3. Description of Sample and Sampling Procedures

The study employed both probability and non-probability sampling procedures to select target groups in the study. This is explained below

2.3.1 Sampling of Schools

The sampled schools consisted of two national schools, two extra county schools, five county schools and five sub county schools. For ethical issues, county and sub county

schools were randomly assigned letters A, B, C, D, E... There are two national schools and two extra county schools in West Pokot whereby all were sampled. The names of faculties remained the same. This confidentiality was maintained due to the nature of sensitivity associated with performance of schools. Stratified random sampling method was adopted in selecting five county schools (A, B, C, D and E) and five sub-county schools (F, G, H, I and J). The basis for stratification was school category, specifically county and sub county schools. Stratified sampling resulted in selecting schools both county and sub county schools, which were geographically situated in West Pokot County and within the Rift Valley. The researcher did not consider this scenario as a limitation because the research design adopted allows generalisation of findings to the whole population, that is, the whole constituency of schools in Kenya.

The selected schools constituted 23% of their respective population. This choice was justified by homogeneity criterion of 10 % as advanced by Kerlinger (2004), who recommends a sample size of at least 10% and 25% for homogeneous and heterogeneous population respectively. In this study, the homogeneity was in terms of departments, work experience and year of study orientation.

2.3.2 Sampling of Students

The study employed probability sampling technique to select students who participated in the study. The lists of students were obtained from Director of Studies offices. The study was not interested in gender as a sampling criterion as most schools were of single gender. The students were classified as under their category of school. Stratified sampling method was deemed appropriate. A total of 229 questionnaires were administered to the students. 40 for national schools, 40 for extra county schools, 78 for county schools and 71 for sub county schools. The students, who participated in the study, were selected using stratified then systematic sampling techniques.

2.3.3 Sampling of Heads of Departments, Principals and County and Ministry of Education Officials

All the heads of department from the sampled schools were automatically included in the study. Principals of the selected schools were considered instrumental in providing relevant data on various dimensions of the study. County and Ministry of Education officials were selected on availability as they were few.

2.3.4 Sample Size and Sampling Procedures

The study used both probability and non-probability designs, specifically cluster and purposive sampling techniques. According to Saifuddin Ahmed (2009), cluster

sampling is appropriate where a group of population elements constitutes the sampling unit, instead of a single element of the population. This was important in this research as the target population comprised of groups. The main reason for choosing cluster sampling was its cost efficiency in terms of economy and feasibility. The research also used purposive sampling to get the specific respondents from the clusters. Purposive sampling was appropriate as it allows the researcher choose specific people within the cluster to use for a particular study. One of the key benefits of this sampling method is the ability to gather large amounts of information by using a range of different techniques. This variety will in turn give you a better cross-section of information.

The purposive and disproportionate selection at the level of respondents allowed for equal allocation which is important because the study required the researcher to make comparisons between clusters for statistical analysis and to draw conclusions.

Table 1: Sampling Frame of Students and Schools

s/ n o	Category of School	Total Number of Schools per Category	Number of Schools Picked per Category	Total Number of Students Per Category	Number of Students picked per Category
1	National School	2	2	567	40
2	Extra-county School	2	2	536	40
3	County School	18	5	221	78
4	Sub-county School	37	5	252	71
Total		59	14	1576	229

(Comprised of form four students only)

2.4 Data Collection Instruments

2.4.1 Questionnaires

Questionnaire method was used to collect data from students and heads of departments. The questionnaire was considered appropriate in this case as it provided a more comprehensive view than any other research tool. Questionnaire was used to obtain primary data from the sampled population. All the respondents were asked the same questions in the same order. The questionnaire contained both open and closed ended questions. It was standardized and completely pre-determined. The questionnaires produced both qualitative and quantitative data. The main advantage of the instrument was that it allowed the researcher control and focus responses to the

research objectives thus enhancing relevancy of data collected. Questionnaires were used to collect data on stakeholders' perception on abolition of ranking of schools in National examinations, effect of abolition of school ranking on students' commitment to academic performance, and how abolition of school ranking influences parents commitment to academic performance.

2.4.2 Interview Schedules

Information was also to be collected from key informants by use of interview schedule. This included interviewing PTA chairpersons, School Principals and Ministry of Education officials. This was because of the role they play in the education sector as a whole. The interview schedule was important as it helped elicit effective responses from the respondents regarding the subject of the study. The information collected formed part of the primary data. The interview schedule comprised of structured and semi-structured questions on how abolition of ranking influences Ministry and County officials' commitment to academic performance in West Pokot County.

2.5 Data Analysis Procedures

Quantitative data was analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. chi-square was used to determine the relationship between various aspects of study. Qualitative data was organized, caterised and analysed in form of themes and narratives.

2.6 Ethical Considerations

Permission to carry out the study was sought from National Council for Science, Technology and Innovation (NACOSTI) and from the participants who participated in the study. The nature and purpose of the research was explained to the respondents by the researcher. The researcher respected the individual's rights to safeguard their personal integrity. During the course of data collection, the respondents were assured of anonymity, confidentiality and they were assured of their ability to withdraw from the study at any time if they wished to do so. No names or personal identification numbers reflected on the questionnaires except the numbering for questionnaires which is for purposes of identification of data during editing. Finally, the results of the study were availed to the relevant authority and to those participants who were willing to know the results.

3. Summary of Findings, Conclusion and Recommendations

3.1 Summary of findings

The study was carried out to analyze the effect of abolition of ranking in national examination in West Pokot County. Data was collected by use of questionnaires and interview schedules. Data was analyzed using descriptive statistics and inferential statistics. A total of 34 teachers, 229 students, 7 principals and 4 county education officers were involved in the study. Findings can be summarized as follows as per the objectives:

3.1.1 Stakeholders' Perception on Abolition of Ranking of Students and Schools in Examinations

Analysis on stakeholders' perception on abolition of ranking of students and schools in examinations is presented in table 2

Table 2: Stakeholders' Perception on Abolition of Ranking of Students and Schools in Examinations

Statement	SD	D	UND	AG	SAG
	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)
Ranking motivates teachers to cover syllabus	5(14.7)	2(5.9)	2(5.9)	10(29.4)	15(44.5)
Ranking among departments encourages competition	0(0)	5(14.7)	6(17.6)	13(38.2)	10(29.4)
Ranking enhances interschool competition	4(11.8)	2(5.9)	5(14.7)	9(26.5)	14(41.2)
Ranking creates unhealthy competition between different categories of schools	9(26.5)	4(11.8)	4(11.8)	6(17.6)	11(32.4)
Ranking encourages malpractices	5(14.7)	7(20.6)	4(11.8)	5(14.7)	13(38.2)
Teachers are geared in their teachings to the examination but not learning	3(6.8)	8(23.5)	6(17.6)	7(20.6)	10(29.4)
Ranking leads to concentration of examinations and ignore dimensions.	5(14.7)	2(5.9)	7(20.6)	7(20.6)	10(29.4)
Ranking results to narrowing of curriculum	5(14.7)	3(6.8)	6(17.6)	11(32.4)	9(26.5)
Ranking serves as a motivation to students performance	2(5.9)	8(23.5)	8(23.5)	8(23.5)	8(23.5)
Ranking provides feedback to the teacher on the effectiveness of teaching and student achievement	5(14.7)	3(6.8)	6(17.6)	10(29.4)	10(29.4)
Ranking communicates to the teacher what has been learnt	4(11.8)	4(11.8)	4(11.8)	13(38.2)	9(26.5)
Ranking motivates teachers to change instructional practices	4(11.8)	6(17.6)	6(17.6)	11(32.4)	7(20.6)
Ranking has no effect on teachers self-esteem because they regard their role in school as a duty	8(23.5)	5(14.7)	6(17.6)	7(20.6)	8(23.5)

Key: SD- strongly disagree, D- disagree, UND- undecided, AG- agree, SAG- strongly agree. F- Frequency.

Based on findings from head of departments, majority of respondents affirmed that ranking motivates teachers to cover syllabus in which. It was also evident that ranking among departments encourages competition which can lead to positive results. However, majority of the respondents agreed to the belief that ranking encourages competition among schools which can steer to betterment of results. Additionally, the findings implied that ranking creates unhealthy competition between different categories of schools like national school, extra county schools, county schools and sub-county schools and schools should be ranked categorically according to their status. The findings also affirmed that ranking encourages malpractices in examination as some students engage in exam malpractices in order to achieve high grades and make their school ranked higher than other schools. Majority of the respondents agreed that teachers are geared to teach towards passage of examination and not to instill knowledge to students due to ranking. However, it was also evident that ranking makes students to only concentrate on examination and not to also concentrate on other aspects of education. It was also found that the interviewed heads of department agreed to the aspect that ranking leads to narrowing of curriculum. Ranking serves as motivation towards student's performance as when students are ranked higher, they are motivated to work harder and maintain the higher rank. It was also found that ranking communicates to the teacher on what has been learnt in that, in case of a positive deviation from the previous rank, teachers are assured that what was taught or revised was well undertaken. The findings also indicated that Majority of the respondents believed that ranking provide feedback to the teacher on effectiveness of teaching and students' achievement as teachers teach expecting improvement in students' performance. It was also found that ranking motivates teachers to change institutional practices that they find it necessary to change, as majority of the respondents attested to it. The findings showed that ranking has no effect on teachers' self-esteem as they regard their role in school as a duty.

On the general view of ranking, most respondents spoke of abolition of ranking impacting negatively on performance in schools. Most issues raised by the respondents include of students and teachers towards academic performance. From majority of the respondents, it was found that abolition of ranking resulted to drop in levels of academic performance and the decision and the decision should be reverted. On impact of ranking on parental commitment on students' academic performance, it was found that ranking impacts negatively on involvement in students' academic performance. On how abolition of ranking affects performance, it was found that ranking results to poor performance. One of the comments to support this was, "stakeholders will relax knowing that they are not compared with others. However, it was also found that,

ranking impacts negatively on the ministry on aspects such as allocation of resources, students' placement, and effective evaluation of school and also government involvement in specific schools. Another finding was abolition of ranking affected teachers' performance, most of the respondents said that abolition of ranking increases laxity among teachers in support for students and their efforts won't be recognized. It was also found that continued ranking of schools in the county should continue despite its abolition in the county. On this, some say that it's a good move and the government should think of reverting it.

3.1.2 Students' Perception on Abolition of Ranking Effects on Students' Academic Performance

Findings from the study indicated that ranking doesn't leads to negative perception on performance, majority, as its belief that ranking is only associated with positive performance. It was also found that ranking doesn't destroy students' morale at school. The analysis on students' perceptions on abolition of ranking on academic performance is presented in table 3;

Table 3: Students' Perception on Abolition of Ranking Effects on Students' Academic Performance

Aspect	SD	D	UND	AG	SAG
	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)
Ranking leads to negative perception on performance	113(49.3)	47(20.5)	15(6.6)	32(14.0)	22(9.6)
Ranking destroys students morale	89(38.5)	55(24)	19(8.3)	34(14.8)	32(14)
Ranking leads to under enrolment in some schools	38(16.6)	18(7.9)	20(8.7)	73(31.9)	80(34.9)
Lack of ranking leads to poor performance as a result of poor administration and leadership practices	42(18.3)	31(13.5)	11(4.8)	54(23.6)	91(39.7)
Ranking do not provide a systematic and intervention system to improve learner achievement	98(42.8)	47(20.5)	23(10)	33(14.4)	28(12.2)

Key: SD- strongly disagree, D- disagree, UND- undecided, AG- agree, SAG- strongly agree. F- Frequency

This phenomenon is premised on the fact, ranking motivates students to steer forward to achieve better ranks or maintain them. From the findings, it was also evident that lack of ranking leads to poor performance as a result of poor administration and leadership practice. Majority of the respondents disagreed with the notion that ranking does not provide a systematic and intervention system to improve learner achievement. This is because the notion is in contrary to belief that the purpose of ranking is to enhance students' performance and achievement. It also was found that ranking affects students' preparation in examinations. Ranking makes some students to work hard in

order to achieve the best rank. However, it was found that students become less concerned about performance when ranking is abolished as supported by majority of the respondents. Moreover, the findings indicated that ranking hampered students' performance.

3.1.3 How Abolition of Ranking Influences on Parental Commitment towards Academic Performance

The study determined to establish the influence of abolition of ranking on parental commitment towards academic performance. The analysis in Table 4 supports this position.

Table 4: Influence of Abolition of Ranking on Parental Commitment towards Academic Performance

Aspect	SD	D	UND	AG	SAG
	F (%)				
Abolition of ranking influences parents to buy extra teaching and learning materials	54(23.6)	33(14.4)	20(8.7)	52(22.7)	70(30.6)
Abolition of Ranking Influences parental support for homework	78(34.1)	52(22.7)	30(13.1)	35(15.3)	34(14.8)
Abolition of Ranking impacts negatively on parental involvement on school academic programs	47(20.5)	47(20.5)	25(10.9)	40(17.5)	70(30.6)

Key: SD- strongly disagree, D- disagree, UND- undecided, AG- agree, SAG- strongly agree. F- Frequency

It was found that abolition of ranking influences parents to buy extra teaching and learning materials. This is due to a notion that parents wouldn't know the progress of their children in absence of ranking. It was also that ranking does not influence parental support for homework as majority of the respondents attested to this. The findings also indicated that majority of the respondents agreed that abolition of ranking impacts negatively on parental involvement in academic programs.

3.1.4 Ministry of Education and County officials' perception on abolition of ranking to commitment in academic performance in West Pokot County

It was found that on the impact of ranking on performance, ranking resulted in poor performance in schools. Another finding was that ranking doesn't impact on parental involvement in students' performance as parents support their children irrespective their ranks. However, another finding was: abolition of ranking will impact negatively on performance. A claim to ascertain this is, "it will negatively affect performance since the rate of competition would have gone down." On impact of abolition of ranking on

Ministry of Education, it was found that majority claimed that it will impact negatively on involvement in activities such as student placement and monitoring development.

3.2 Hypothesis Testing

Ho1: Relationship between Abolition of Ranking, Syllabus Coverage and Interschool Competition.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.
Ordinal by Ordinal Gamma	.555	.159	3.088	.002
N of Valid Cases	34			

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

The null hypothesis was rejected; the study concluded that there is a significant relationship between syllabus coverage and interschool competition. This indicates that syllabus coverage and interschool competition goes hand in hand and depends on each other.

Ho2: Association of Abolition of Ranking on Teachers changing Institutional Practices and gearing their Teachings towards Examination.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.
Ordinal by Ordinal Gamma	.667	.135	4.440	.000
N of Valid Cases	34			

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

The null hypothesis was rejected; the study concluded that there is significant relationship between teaching /instructional practices and examination preparation. The two factors are dependent on each other.

Ho3: Relationship between Abolition of Ranking on Parental support for homework and Involvement in students' Academic Activities

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.158	.071	2.192	.028
N of Valid Cases		229			

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

The null hypothesis was rejected; the study concluded that there is significant association between Abolition of ranking influences parents to buy extra teaching and learning materials and parental support for homework

Ho4: Relationship between Students’ level of Performance and Abolition of Ranking

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.277	.076	-3.573	.000
N of Valid Cases		229			

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

The null hypothesis was rejected; the study concluded that there is significant relationship between students’ level of performance and abolition of ranking concern on results.

4. Conclusion

From findings and summary, the study concludes that:

Ranking motivates teachers to cover syllabus. They do so in order to put their students at better chance of getting better scorers and put their school in a better rank than other schools or get better mean than other subjects.

Ranking also encourages competition among departments. It also contributes to unhealthy completion among different categories of schools like the national schools, extra county schools, county school and sub-county schools. However, ranking results in interschool competition when schools of the same levels get ranked.

Ranking also result in malpractices in national examination. Students and teachers may engage in orthodox methods of achieving better results in order to achieve better rank than other schools. Abolition of ranking results in narrowing of school’s

curriculum where school's personnel tend to oppose policies linking assessment to accountability on the grounds of perverse effects including narrowing the curriculum.

Ranking also act as motivating factor to performing students as they may put more and more efforts in order to achieve better results or maintain top rank. Ranking also communicates to the teacher on what has been learnt as better through continuous assessment tests, teachers may know areas which were well understood and those that still need revision. Moreover, with ranking teachers are geared to teach towards examination and not to other aspects of education. Ranking also motivates teachers to change institutional practices as well as provide feedback on effectiveness of teaching and learning as a general and also students' achievement.

Ranking however does not have any effect on teacher's self-esteem as they know their defined roles and duties. It also result in negative perception of performance as students may think that it's all about better rank forgetting the prime role if schools is to instill knowledge to students.

Ranking also destroys morale of non-performing students as they get demoralized and feel inferior compared to their colleagues. It also result in under enrollment in schools as school's admiration would try to get only the top performers leaving out those who underperformed.

Ranking also provide a systematic and intervention system to improve learner achievement. Abolition of ranking influences parents to buy extra teaching and learning materials. Abolition of ranking however does not influence parental support for homework. Abolition of ranking impacts negatively on parental involvement on school academic programs

There is a significant relationship between syllabus coverage and interschool competition. This indicates that syllabus coverage and interschool competition goes hand in hand and depends on each other. There is also significant relationship between teaching /instructional practices and examination preparation. The two factors are dependent on each other. There is significant association between Abolition of ranking influences parents to buy extra teaching and learning materials and parental support for homework. In studying relationship between students' level of performance and abolition of ranking concern on results, there was significant relationship between the two factors.

5. Recommendations

From the findings and conclusion, the following recommendations were made:

The decision of abolishing of ranking by government should be reverted as from the findings there is enough evidence that it has a great impact of students' and teachers' performance. Teachers will be able to complete their syllabus in time, provide a good competition among schools of the same category which can result in betterment of results. On malpractices that may arise from ranking, government should enact strict measures to curb the vice. Teachers should also be educated on their roles and duties to make them avoid exerting pressure to students to perform better and should not only think of examination passage but also to remember on impacting knowledge to students.

Ranking should also be done continuously as parents may get to know progress of their children at school as well as to know specific areas in which they need to focus in provision of academic and moral support such as support for homework. Parents should also be educated on ranking so that they will not punish their children in case they get lower ranks but provide them with necessary support.

Schools should provide psychological support to all students especially underperforming ones. This will enable reduce the negative perception of ranking on performance from students as well as boost their morale. Teachers should also work hard in their teachings irrespective of presence or absence of ranking to improve performance as well provides better administrative and leadership practices. Schools should also seek better methods of improving students' performance but not to punish them or discontinue others to suit their ambitions as this may result in under enrollment in schools.

Ministry of Education should provide resource and moral support to schools irrespective of ranking positions or its presence or absence and treat schools equally.

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